

AUTUMN IMAGERY AND CHARACTER SPIRIT IN OYDIN HOJIYEVA'S POMS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the image of autumn in the poems of Aydin Khojiev, the owner of a great soul who was able to show the power of artistic words for the motherland, the brilliant creator, its expression, was written through various similes. We may not observe the expression of images of nature in an artist who is the queen of her people. The expression of the image of autumn through poetic verses in the article is an artistic reflection of the soul of the poetess, who has become an artist through beautiful lines.

Key words: artistic images, inner experience, landscape lyric, lyrical hero, creative soul, natural beauty

INTRODUCTION

Aydin Khojiev, the honored poetess of our nation, is a creator who has her own place and role among female poets in the modern literature of the 21st century. His poems are completely different from the poetry of other authors due to their elegance, melodiousness, attractiveness, and richness of images. Through most of our studies, we focused on the image of nature, image of spring, image of summer in the works of Aydin Khojiev. Today, we will pay attention to the poems of the poetess, in which the image of autumn was written.

METHODS

Star showers are falling.

Saksavul, the selves are bathed in light

The rider of time is the wind

Clamour will pass the slumbering shore

In Aydin Khojiev's poems, I mean nature, the image of autumn is interpreted as a means of giving the reader aesthetic pleasure, a lyrical mood, and a comforting place for a troubled heart. The sky-high mountains, the paths with flowers growing on their banks, the sky as clear as glass, white fluffy clouds, trees with branches reaching up to

the sky, quiet forests, and the singing of partridges in the charming oasis of the artist will open your heart. the sun burning like the mouth of an oven, the juniper tree, under whose green leaves you can see blueberry fruits like peas, brings joy to the hearts; the air of the desert, its vastness, the moon floating in the yellow mist, the rivers that make a muffled sound and gurgle like a mythical creature calm the reader's heart. These views are not images based on some external observation. All the beauties on earth and in the sky are not embodied in the eyes of the writer at once, at the same time. One of the main features of the creative principle of the poetess is to depict nature in every way, to the smallest detail, with deep knowledge.[1]

RESULTS

We pay our attention to the poem "Autumn Sky" from the author's book "Evening Lights":

A cloud suitable for the autumn sky,
Cranes with a friendly smile.
Forget the silence of the autumn sky,
Mountains to the dome of the sky.[2]

Autumn season is one of the most beautiful seasons that pleases the human tongue. For many people, autumn is considered a season of separation and separation because of the yellowing of the leaves. But the autumn season in the work of the poetess is special and attractive: the autumn sky is very beautiful and elegant. Its sky is beautiful, even if it is not clear, and the clouds suit it. Clouds add beauty to the sky. The cranes swaying like a sheep fly in the sky. We do not see silence in the autumn sky. It has noises like the roar of mountains. In the autumn, the sardine goes around the tree and eats the delicious fruits. The mouths of the pilgrims are drooling when they see the delicacies spread on the autumn table. At this time of autumn, the quinces are golden on the tree, and the pomegranates are starting to burst. Antique stones glisten in streams like necklaces strung on a string. At this time of autumn, the work is very intense, someone is pressing alfalfa on the roof, and someone is inspecting the furrows. When working people come tired from work and listen to the ground, they feel a kind of rustling and a feeling of wakefulness. It is at this moment that endless dreams float like ships at the foot of the horizon. The trees also throw off their blue coats and begin to eat the winter sorrow. This kind of beauty and charm opens the heart of a person. In this poem of the artist, the beauty of nature is described on a large scale. With the help of the landscape, the poet created beautiful images. That is why the poem was liked by the reader. Let's pay attention to another poem about autumn:

Thoughtful autumn days, in pleasant gardens.

The letters of opportunity are redeemed.

In stallions swaying in the wind

The joys of childhood.

In this poem, the autumn season is described in a bright image. It is said that in autumn, the sun burns slowly, as if calming nature, preparing it for a long winter sleep. The fiery colors of the leaves, falling from the branches, spreading a soft carpet under the feet of those who shoot, and falling to the ground are expressed through beautiful images. In the poem, the air is filled with such purity that it is clear and melodious, like a stretched thread. Outdoors, the cloudless sky is so close that you can reach out and touch this pink color. When it is dragged by the clouds, the earth seems to be covered with a gray soft and at the same time dense blanket. The closer the cold winter is, the more autumn cries with cold rains and sighs with cold winds, which makes you think about eternity and feel a little sad. After the rain, the smell of fallen leaves and dead horses remains, which tickles the nose pleasantly, and one wants to inhale this smell again and again, remember it and keep it in mind until the next autumn.

I found the conglomerate of spring,

The flowers bloomed in the meadows,

I kissed the yellow dress of autumn,

Dice leaves picked in gardens

"If you are a poet and the navos of ancient ancestors are playing in your soul, sing this! If the spirit of the changing era has entered your soul, search for new forms." This time of the year is the most lively period for the poetess! Indeed, autumn reveals nature, which shows the world in completely different colors, first bright, watery, then gray and dull. This changeable, unstable autumn turns hot summers into cold winters year after year and causes them to say goodbye each time.

In this season, where there is an elegant silence, a silent breeze, and a pure elegance, you will be fascinated by the beauty of autumn and flow in the amber flood. According to the poet, each month of the autumn season has a slightly different character. August, when cancer is cut off, the river tributary is clear, and grapes like "shakarangur" and "bride's finger" are plucked in the vineyards at dawn, is as follows in Aydin Hojiyeva's image: in the summer season, she builds a cellar in the gardens and invites the peasants to visit the gardens. Seeing a little reflection in the minds of the peasants, a devilish feeling in his mind falls to the sky. In the early morning, a soft

dew like a masterpiece touches the fragrant leaves of figs, and at this time, a cool wind blows in the mountains and near the valley.

Summer is dying,

The river tributary flows clear.

Dawn breaks in the vineyards,

"Shakarangur, "Bride's finger.[4]

DISCUSSION

Oydin Hajiyeva's poems reflect the attitude of man to man, nature, society and theology, and the poet interprets the traditional symbols and artistic images that have been formed over the centuries, based on his thoughts and observations, and his philosophical worldview in a new way. Literary scholar U.Toychiyev recognized that the lyrical hero is the king of the kingdom of subjectivity I as one of the important characteristics of the lyrical hero [5] - . This "I" is considered not only to the poet's inner self, but also to the reader's inner world and psyche. That is why the singing lion sounds like our little feelings and emotional experiences. We accept it as our own. This shows the artist's skill. The golden leaves that catch the eye on the top branches of the trees will touch the heart of the person who has planted all his love in the lip of the flower. A goldfinch with sun marks on its wings also flies away. Golden spikes begin to appear in the sky like a yellow star. The autumn season is compared to the "honeymoon" of the bride and groom after the wedding. The dowry of the lucky girl is ready to go on her honeymoon. Nature, like parents, hesitates about the upcoming wedding.

CONCLUSION

In the above poems, he describes the relationship between nature and man as lack of feelings. It is like traveling to the beautiful gardens of the poetess, not to an outside world, where Aydin Khojiyeva's works were published during her lifetime. He is inspired by the spring scenery and joys of these gardens, looking at their state in the embrace of autumn, sometimes happy, sometimes sad, sometimes sad.

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